

Studies in Mixed Liquid Crystals of Structurally Similar Mesomorphs and Non-mesomorphs

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Two homologous series of mesogens viz *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates¹ (I) and *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates² (II) have been synthesised. Three binary systems of the homologues of these series have been explored here. The first two binary systems consist of homologues of series (I); binary system 1 consisting the homologues *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-hexyloxycinnamate K 87° S 118° N 124° IA and *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-decyloxycinnamate, K 78° S 123° IB and binary system 2 consisting the homologues *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-ethoxycinnamate K 135° IA and *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-butoxycinnamate K 98.5° S 108° N 122° IB. The binary system 3 consists of homologues of series², II, viz. *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-ethoxycinnamate K 168° IA and *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-*n*-butoxycinnamate K 116° N 120.5° IB. In binary system 1, the overall mixed smectic characteristic predominates over a wide range of temperature and concentration. The mixed nematic phase does not extend beyond above 30 mole% of the smectic mesogen (B). The N-I and S-I curves deviate very little from the rule of linearity. Contrary to which the binary system 2 indicates predominance of the mixed nematic character, the N-I curve follows an ideal pattern. The S-N curve shows the steep rising tendency as the concentration of the nematogen (B) increases similar to one found in the case of pure homologous series exhibiting polymesomorphism^{1,2}. The binary system 3 presents similarity with other binary systems studied³, the characteristic effects due to the magnitude of the dipole moments of the NO₂ group are discernible. The N-I curve deviates from the rule of linearity though the components comprising the system are identical in all respects in their molecular geometry.

BINARY mixtures, both components of which are liquid crystals, are known to form continuous mixed liquid crystals⁴. Most of them do not undergo any change in their mesomorphic textures⁵⁻⁷ though a few have been reported giving rise to different textures⁸. Binary mixtures, none, one or, both components of which are liquid crystals, have been studied in sufficient details over the years and the findings have been quite interesting and enlightening. Emergence of mixed mesophase where none existed earlier, increase or decrease of mixed mesophase ranges and thermal stabilities and the study of the factors that influence the modifications are some of the aspects which have received greater attention. We have reported a mixture where a higher order smectic phase emerges from mixtures of two nematogens⁹.

Here we present the study of three binary mixtures selected from two homologous series namely *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates (binary systems I and II), and *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates (binary system III). The results are found to be most interesting in terms of the predominance of mixed smectic characteristics in system I, mixed

nematic characteristics in system II and indicating the deviation from the rule of linearity in the case of system III.

Experimental

Preparation of the homologues: *p*-*n*-Alkoxybenzaldehydes, *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamic acids and *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyl chlorides were prepared by the reported methods⁹⁻¹¹.

The components of the binary systems were selected from the homologous series, viz. *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates¹ (binary systems 1 and 2) and *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates² (binary system 3); the synthesis of the homologues have been described earlier^{1,2}.

The transitions and other characteristics of the mixtures of these binary systems were studied using a Kofler heating stage polarizing microscope. The results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The first binary system consists of two components of the same homologous series, viz. *p*-chlorophenyl

TABLE I—TRANSITION OF BINARY SYSTEMS

Mole % of A	Transitions		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
System : (A) <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl <i>p</i> '-n-hexyloxy-cinnamate			
(B) <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl <i>p</i> '-n-decyloxy-cinnamate			
100.00	87.0	118.0	124.0
91.20	78.0	117.0	121.5
82.24	65.0	117.0	121.5
72.94	62.5	—	120.0
63.41	56.5	—	119.0
53.62	53.5	—	120.0
43.53	49.0	—	121.0
33.12	55.5	—	122.0
22.43	58.5	—	122.5
11.35	63.0	—	122.5
00.00	78.0	—	123.0

Sintering point = 49°

 System : (A) *p*-Chlorophenyl *p*'-ethoxycinnamate
 (B) *p*-Chlorophenyl *p*'-n-butoxycinnamate

100.00	—	—	135.0
90.79	—	—	134.5
81.35	—	—	129.0
71.82	—	(117.5)	126.5
62.12	—	113.5	120.0
52.21	—	107.0	119.5
42.13	—	103.5	119.0
31.90	84.5	96.0	119.5
21.48	97.5	106.5	121.5
10.81	98.5	107.5	121.5
00.00	98.5	108.0	122.0

Sintering point = 84.5°

 System : (A) *p*-Nitrophenyl *p*'-ethoxycinnamate
 (B) *p*-Nitrophenyl *p*'-n-butoxycinnamate

100.00	—	—	163.0
90.73	—	—	163.0
81.35	—	—	154.5
71.76	—	—	152.0
62.00	—	—	151.5
52.15	—	—	150.0
42.07	—	(112.5)	138.0
31.83	—	(114.0)	126.0
21.38	—	109.5	113.5
10.81	—	112.5	115.5
00.00	—	116.0	120.5

Sintering point = 108.5°

Value in parenthesis indicates monotropy.

p'-n-alkoxycinnamates. Component (A) is C₆-member, poly-mesomorphic and component (B) is C₁₀-member, a pure smectogen. Besides measuring the depression in the K-M transition, the idea is to discover the extent to which the poly-mesomorphic property can persist. The phase diagram (Fig. 1) shows that the K-M transition is the lowest at about 57 mole % of the component B (smectogenic), and this eutectic temperature is 49°. Taking the difference between the K-M transition of the component (A) and the eutectic temperature, the depression is of 38°, which is quite good. However, the smectic mesophase length above the eutectic point is 72° which is indeed a wide range, the N-I and S-I curves do not depress much and can be said to follow the rule of ideality with minor deviations. The poly-mesomorphic region does not extend beyond 17.5 mole % of (B) which indicates the predominance of highly smectogenic property of (B). The S-N

 Fig. 1. System I: (A) *p*-Chlorophenyl *p*'-n-hexyloxy-cinnamate, (B) *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-n-decyloxy-cinnamate.

curve almost remains parallel. The dotted line in the curve indicates the possibility of mixed mesophase formation upto factual composition 22 mole % of (B). The decrease in nematic phase range with increase in concentration of pure smectic component (B) (C₁₀-homologue) is indicative of the fact that the homologues beyond the C₆-member (A) (poly-mesomorphs) will have greater and predominating lateral attractions giving rise to only smectic mesophase formation. The second binary system also consists of the components of the same homologous series-I, the component (A) in this system is a non-mesogen and (B) is a poly-mesomorph. This system consists of C₂-member (A) and C₄-member (B) of the homologous series-I. The phase diagram (Fig. 2) of this system shows that mesomorphic region beyond poly-mesomorphic sector is all nematic, whereas it was all smectic in the first binary system, which is keeping with the mesomorphic characteristics of the homologous series. The other characteristic of the phase diagram (Fig. 2) of this system no. 2 is that the region between 0.0 and 25 mole % of (B) is non-mesomorphic region which

 Fig. 2. System-II: (A) *p*-Chlorophenyl *p*'-ethoxycinnamate, (B) *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-n-butoxycinnamate.

indicates that terminal attractions of the molecules are insufficient to form mixed nematic phase in this region. The diagram (Fig. 2) then passes from non-mesomorphic to poly-mesomorphic region through pure nematic region with increase in concentration of poly-mesomorphic component (B). The S-N curve shows rising tendency with increase in concentration of (B), which is reminiscent of the S-N curve of pure homologous series¹. However, the mixed smectic phase remains almost of the same width throughout the portion of its existence indicating the increase in ratio of nematic to smectic phase length with decrease in concentration of (B). A very interesting feature of this system is that the N-I curve (Fig. 2) when intrapolated indicates a temperature of 115° which can be the latent transition temperature of the non-mesomorphic component (A). The LTT (I-N transition) is comparable with the one obtained by similarly intrapolating the N-I curve for the even members of the homologous series-1; the value being 117°. These two values can be viewed as in fine agreement, thereby lending credibility to the concept of intrapolation method for determining the LTT^{1,2}. Araya and Matsunaga¹³ studied the systems of Dave and Dewar⁵ and Dave and Lohar⁶ by DSC and esr methods, and they have reported the presence of nematic phase below the isotropic phase. In absence of such facilities available, only intrapolation method deemed to be sufficiently reliable for these systems. It should also be noted that the law of ideality is again followed in the N-I curve of this system (Fig. 2). The third binary system consists of the homologues of series *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates²; component (A) the C₂-homologue and component (B) the C₄-homologue. The C₂-homologue (A) is a non-mesogen and the C₄-homologue (B) is a nematogen with a mesophase range of only 4°. The phase diagram of the system (Fig. 3) shows that the N-I transitions depress successively with increase in concentration of (B) touching a sort of minimum at about 30 mole % of (A) which is in the monotropic region. The N-I curve thus yields a concave shape reminiscent of an incipient rounded minimum a characteristic first observed and contributed to the NO₂ group in the late fifties⁶ and taken as the strong characteristic for formation of mixed liquid crystals. The N-I curve is enantiotropic initially upto about 26 mole % of (A); it enters then into the monotropic region of a short range which cannot be traced beyond about 43 mole % of (A) and then the non-mesomorphic property of (A) predominates. When the N-I curve is intrapolated (Fig. 3) it yields the value of latent transition temperature of the non-mesogen, viz. *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-ethoxycinnamate, which 123.5°. This intrapolated value compares very well with similarly intrapolated value 121° as obtained from the plot of homologous series, viz. *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates. This observation once again strengthens the view that intrapolation can yield quite reliable results. It seems that due to high K-I transitions of (A), the mixed enantiotropic nematic range varies between 4 and 6°; but this nematic range widens up remark-

Fig. 3. System III: (A) *p*-Nitrophenyl *p*'-ethoxycinnamate, (B) *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-*n*-butoxycinnamate.

ably in the monotropic region and assures a realisable maximum value of about 26° below the K-I transition beyond about 24 mole % of (A).

It is quite interesting to note that the first two binary systems differ only in their number of $-\text{CH}_2-$ units of the $-\text{OR}$ chain of the individual homologues functioning as components of the binary systems; the other molecular geometry is identical in all respects. The difference in the $-\text{CH}_2-$ units in 1st binary system is of 4 while that in 2nd binary system is of 2. If the smectogenic characteristic is eliminated from the discussion for the time being, then a relationship of the total mixed mesophase length with the difference in the number of $-\text{CH}_2-$ units can become quite suggestive. The mixed mesophase length at the eutectic concentration of both these systems are about 72 and 36° respectively thus the difference in the mixed mesophase is of 36° for two $-\text{CH}_2-$ units which turns out to be of 18° per $-\text{CH}_2-$ unit. Though no generalisation could be made at this stage, it is interesting enough to record that with more difference in the number of $-\text{CH}_2-$ units of the components, the mixed mesophase length will be increasingly enhanced. But this consideration does not apply to the 3rd binary system the difference in the $-\text{CH}_2-$ units of the components is 2; thus the mixed mesophase length at the eutectic concentration should be expected to be about 36°, but it is only 5°. Since molecular geometry of the components of 3rd binary system is similar to that of 1st and 2nd binary systems, the only difference being the NO₂ group at the right-hand-side in the components of 3rd binary system, it should be responsible for the lapse against the suggested extended mixed mesophase length. The mixed N-I curve deviates from the linearity rule though the components comprising the system are identical in all respects in their molecular geometry; this deviation causing a concavity, should again be attributed to the NO₂ group's high tendency of favouring formation of oriented fluids. While the K-N transitions follow a regular pattern of depression with increasing concentration of (A) within the mixed mesomor-

phic region, the mixed K-I curve the non-mesomorphic region of the phase (Fig. 3) follows a rather erratic depression pattern.

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